

Fertilizer management

Comparative efficiency of *Sesbania*, *Gliricidia*, and urea as N sources in wetland rice

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Sesbania cannabina is a well-recognized green manure (GM) for rice. Farmers have not widely adopted it because they are reluctant to use their land, water, and other inputs for raising a crop exclusively for GM. *Gliricidia sepium*, a perennial leguminous tree, is grown extensively in roadsides, hedges, and field boundaries in the tropics. High foliage yields, vigorous coppicing ability, and tolerance for regular lopping make *Gliricidia* a good GM. Using loppings for GM is popular in many parts of southern India.

We compared efficiency of *Sesbania*, *Gliricidia*, and urea as N sources for rice variety Rasi in a Vertisol with 0.92% organic C, 0.10% total N, and pH 7.9 during 1988 dry season (DS).

The equivalent of 100 kg N/ha from each source was supplied to rice crops. A no-N control was also used. Eight-wk-

old *Sesbania* plants (from a different field) and 1-m-long tender *Gliricidia* loppings (collected from hedges) were chopped into 10-15 cm pieces for incorporation into the puddled field as a single basal dose at 2 d before transplanting. On a fresh weight basis, the *Sesbania* samples contained 0.50% total N, and the *Gliricidia*, 0.64% total N. Urea was applied in two equal splits at transplanting and 57 d later at panicle initiation (PI) stage. The 2 M KCl extractable $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ in soil under the different N treatments was monitored through the first 8 wk after transplanting (WAT). Rice grain yield and total N uptake at PI and at maturity were evaluated.

Urea was the most efficient of the N sources. Efficiency of *Gliricidia* N and *Sesbania* N was about 67% and 45%, respectively, that of urea N. Crop N uptake from *Gliricidia* was significantly higher than from *Sesbania* at both PI and maturity. Rice yield using *Gliricidia* was 0.6 t/ha more than with *Sesbania*.

Gliricidia released relatively more N to the soil than *Sesbania* through 8 WAT.

While the rice crop was growing, mean available N content in the soil (0-15 cm plow layer) treated with *Gliricidia* was 16.6 kg/ha and 13.9 kg/ha with *Sesbania*. Availability of N to the rice crop from *Gliricidia* at early tillering stage (4 WAT) was significantly higher than that from *Sesbania* (see table).

Gliricidia seems to be more promising than *Sesbania* as a GM source of N for wetland rice. ■

Efficiency of 3 N sources in rice variety Rasi in a submerged Vertisol. Rajendranagar, Hyderabad, India, 1988 DS.

N source	Available N ^a content in soil (kg/ha)						N uptake by rice (kg/ha)		Rice grain yield (t/ha)
	Days after transplanting						PI	Maturity	
	2	7	14	28	42	56			
None	10.9	13.4	13.4	7.5	7.4	1.3	49.4	69.0	3.9
Urea ^b	46.8	42.2	39.1	17.0	3.8	2.7	91.6	146.0	6.6
<i>Sesbania</i>	20.1	20.5	20.7	15.2	4.7	2.1	70.9	102.1	5.1
<i>Gliricidia</i>	18.6	22.2	22.2	29.2	4.8	2.7	87.0	114.2	5.7
LSD (0.05)	4.3	2.9	3.8	2.6	1.0	0.9	9.0	8.2	0.8

^a2 M KCl extractable $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ in 0-15 cm plow layer. ^bApplied in two equal splits at transplanting and 57 d later.

Fertilizer management—inorganic sources

Effect of lignite fly ash (LFA) on rice

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We evaluated the effect of LFA on dry matter production (DMP) of rice cultivar IR20 grown in a lateritic sandy clay loam soil in Kadampuliyur village, South Arcot District, TN, during Jun-Sep 1987 and Dec 1987-Apr 1988. Analysis of LFA (obtained from Thermal Power Plant, Neyveli, TN, India) indicated pH of 10, EC 1.0 dS/m, 49% SiO_2 , 12% CaO, 6.3% MgO, 8.3% K_2O , 300 ppm

available SiO_2 , and no N and P.

The experimental soil had pH 5.5, EC 0.1 dS/m, 0.17% organic C, 70 ppm available SiO_2 (low), 70 ppm available N (low), 2.8 ppm Olsen's P (low), and 83 ppm available K (low). Soil was air-dried, sieved, and put into clay pots at 10 kg/pot. In the first season, LFA was applied at 5 g/pot (1 t/ha). Nutrient treatments were N, NP, NK, and NPK, with and without LFA (Table 1). The experiment was laid out in a completely randomized design with four replications.

Rainwater was added to the pots, which were then submerged for 10 d, We applied N as urea at 40 ppm, P as

Table 1. DMP and P and SiO_2 content of rice when LFA was applied in lateritic sandy clay loam soil.^a 1987.

Treatment	DMP (g/pot)	Nutrient content			
		P (ppm)	SiO_2 (%)		
N	11.07	c	295	e	3.09
N + LFA	11.36	c	350	c	3.95
N + P	13.39	bc	323	d	2.90
N + P + LFA	14.83	b	362	c	3.11
N + K	9.56	d	309	de	2.95
N + K + LFA	10.74	b	421	b	2.40
N + P + K	15.99	cd	328	d	3.16
N + P + K + LFA	22.70	a	569	a	2.86
LSD (P=0.05)	3.09		19		ns ^b

^aValues followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bns = not significant.